

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: MIHRETU****FIRST NAME: BELETE****PROGRAM CODE: DEPI****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author used Turabian parenthetical/in-text/ references

The author did *not* use Zotero to insert references

The author did not use Grammarly Premium

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 10)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. In conducting research, having sources is an initial step; critical evaluation of the relevance and reliability of the source comes next. The **reliability** of the source can be checked by asking all the following questions, except¹:

- Is the source published by a reputable press?
- Is the source published in the previous less than 5 years?*
- Has it been peer-reviewed?
- Does it include bibliographic data?

¹ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 45.

2. While sources consulted online follow similar rules in the citation as other similar printed sources, a lot of such references may not have complete information to be cited, and their contents can be revised without notice; still, such sources may be simultaneously available from more than one site. Choose the **best way** to tackle such problems among the given choices.²
- Use recent days programs like EndNote, RefWorks, and Zotero.
 - Locating the Uniform Resource Locator (URL) of the source consulted and saving a screenshot of the source?
 - Citing URL sources in a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) by appending them to <https://doi.org/>*
 - Always keep at least two copies of citations-library data.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018),144.

3. Which of the following **may not** risk us a charge of plagiarism?^{3,4}
- Not citing every piece of information we incorporate in our writing, particularly when writing about common knowledge that can be found in numerous areas.*
 - Citing a source accurately when using the exact words of the source, not identifying them as a quotation.
 - Unintentionally not citing a source accurately.
 - Not giving credit to the author of the source of information where the borrowed resource is only a statistic/data, or visuals (such as a graph).
4. Latin abbreviations are appropriate in all of the following **except**:⁵
- In business, formal, and technical writing*
 - footnotes
 - bibliographies
 - informal writing (e.g., the information in parentheses).

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 371-381

⁴ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 34-37.

⁵ *Ibid.*, 59.

5. Which of the following choices has a **correct** US English format?⁶
- "She screamed, 'I didn't do it!' and then ran away."***
 - 'She screamed, "I didn't do it!" and then ran away.'
 - 'The boy kicked the ball.'
 - Dear Mr Smith,
6. Choose the **incorrect** placement of citation of a source (x) in a footnote or Endnote among the following statements.⁷
- According to Litwack, “Scores of newly freed slaves viewed the movement as a vital expression of their emancipation.”^x
 - According to Litwack^x, “Scores of newly freed slaves viewed the movement as a vital expression of their emancipation.”***
 - “Scores of newly freed slaves viewed the movement as a vital expression of their emancipation,” according to Litwack.^x
 - Litwack argues that “scores of newly freed slaves viewed the movement as a vital expression of their emancipation,”^x and he proceeds to prove this assertion.

⁶ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 31-32

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 371–372.

7. While the elements in notes and bibliography entries follow the same general order for all types of sources (author, title, facts of publication), there are clear distinctive features of notes and bibliographies. Which of the following statements is **not correct** in this regard?⁸
- Notes present authors' names in standard order (first name first), while bibliography entries present them in inverted order (last name first) for alphabetical order.
 - Notes separate most elements with commas while bibliography entries separate them with periods.
 - Unlike a bibliography (which may occasionally include page ranges of sources), notes include specific page numbers.
 - In notes, terms abbreviate (e.g., ed for an editor or edited by); however, in bibliography entries, they are often spelled out when they introduce a name (Edited by...).
 - Unlike in notes, most titles in bibliography entries can be capitalized using headline style and use italics for titles of larger entities (books, journals).*

⁸ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations*. Ninth ed. (Chicago: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 149-155.

8. In the distinction between qualitative and quantitative research, which of the following statements is **not correct**?⁹
- The purpose of quantitative research is to seek consensus (the norm), while it is to delve into the “essence” of the topic in qualitative research.
 - A quantitative research design is determined up front and the design is proposed up front but is open and emergent, rather than rigid.
 - The role of the qualitative researcher is to adopt an etic (outsider) point of view that attempts to remain unbiased while the quantitative researcher adopts an emic (insider) point of view where the researcher is active and involved.*
 - Quantitative research seeks to uphold scientific standards of validity and reliability while qualitative research seeks to establish credibility and dependability by way of triangulation and other strategies.
9. In qualitative studies, perceptions of participants that might not have been revealed through interviews can be uncovered through probing assumptions that rely solely on the respondents’ recall. These methods which often are too abbreviated are called¹⁰:
- Critical incident reports.*
 - Focus group discussions
 - Observations
 - Document reviews

⁹ Linda D. Bloomberg and Marie F. Volpe, *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. (Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019), 137-141.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*, 458-459.

10. In British usage, which of the following is properly punctuated?¹¹

- Alex inquired, “Would you please sign and return the attached form!”
- Alex inquired, “Would you please sign and return the attached form?”
- Alex inquired, “Would you please sign and return the attached form.”***
- Alex inquired: “Would you please sign and return the attached form,”

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie F. Volpe. *Completing your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Fourth ed. Los Angeles: SAGE, 2019.

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¹¹ European Commission, *English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*. Eighth ed. (European Commission: European Union Publications Office, 2021), 15.